

Halogenation of the Condensation Products of Alkyl-*o*-toluidines with Chloral Hydrate and the Nitration of the Resulting Compounds.

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With a view to study the nature of the reactions involved in the nitration of chloral derivatives of phenylalkylamines in which both the *ortho* positions to the amino group are occupied, bromination of the chloral derivatives of alkyl-*o*-toluidines (I, R = Me or Et) was carried out.

Bromine with (I) at ordinary or increased temperatures, with or without iodine as carrier, yielded only monobromo compounds. The position of the bromine atom was established from the fact that these monobromo compounds yielded diacetyl derivatives indicating that both chloral and the amino groups are not affected by the action of bromine. Moreover, the action of alkaline potassium permanganate on the diacetyl derivative of the monobromo compound (II) which should give a dibasic acid containing no bromine atoms if the latter entered the methyl group attached to the nucleus, yielded instead a ketonic acid (III), m.p. 201° containing bromine.

These reactions together with the work on the bromination of aromatic amines by Fries (*Annalen*, 1906, 346, 128) indicate that as in nitration, the bromine atom enters the nucleus in the *ortho* position to the amino group. With chlorine, products similar to the bromo compounds described above, were obtained. In this instance the basic chloral compounds gave impure substances, hence their hydrochlorides were taken for the reaction. The resulting

hydrochlorides were converted into the corresponding bases with ammonia. As with bromo compounds, the acetylation gave diacetyl derivatives.

Nitric acid with the halogenated products of the type (II) yielded bromo- and chloro-chloralphenylalkylnitroamines (IV, X = Br or Cl)

The constitution is confirmed by acetylation when the acetyl group enters the chloral side chain only.

When the nitration product (V) was heated with thionyl chloride, the hydroxyl group in the side chain was replaced by chlorine.

Hence from the study of the nitration of chloral derivatives of (i) alkylnilines, (ii) alkyl-*o*-toluidines (cf. Advani and Wheeler, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1933, 42, 257), and (iii) the halogenation products of the latter at ordinary temperature without the use of a diluent, it was found that the compounds of the type (i) yielded chloral dinitrophenylalkylnitroamines, those of the type (ii) gave chloral mononitrophenylalkylnitroamines and the last only chlorophenylalkylnitroamines, the number of the entrant nitro groups depending upon the presence of replaceable hydrogen in the *ortho* position to the amino group.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Methyl-4-(α -hydroxy- β -trichloroethyl)-6-bromo-N-methylaniline.—*p*-(α -Hydroxy- β -trichloroethyl)-*o*-methyltoluidine (15 g.) and bromine (4.5 g.) were reacted in carbon tetrachloride solution. The resulting precipitate was filtered, washed with carbon tetrachloride and crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol in clusters of needles, m.p. 150°, yield 16.5 g. (C₁₀H₁₁ONCl₃Br requires Halogen, 53.7. Found: Halogen, 53.5 per cent).

The foregoing substance on acetylation gave clusters of prismatic needles from dilute ethanol of 2-methyl-4-(α -acetoxy- β -trichloro-ethyl)-6-bromo-*N*-methylacetanilide, m. p. 130°. (C₁₄H₁₅O₃NCl₃Br requires Halogen, 43.2. Found: Halogen, 42.9 per cent).

3-Methyl-4-(N-acetylmethylamino)-5-bromophenylketonic acid.—The diacetyl derivative (10 g.) was treated at 100° with excess of a mixture of 5% potassium permanganate solution. The filtrate from the precipitated hydrated manganese dioxide, evaporated to half its

bulk, when acidified with strong hydrochloric acid, gave a product which crystallised from boiling water in feathery plates, m. p. 201°. (Found: Br, 25.2. $C_{12}H_{12}O_4NBr$ requires Br, 25.5 per cent).

2-Methyl-4-(α -hydroxy- β -trichloroethyl)-6-bromo-N-ethylaniline.—*p*-(α -Hydroxy- β -trichloroethyl)-*o*-ethyltoluidine (10 g.) was treated with bromine (2.8 g.) and crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 115°, yield 11.2 g. ($C_{11}H_{13}ONCl_3Br$ requires Halogen, 51.6. Found: Halogen, 51.4 per cent).

The foregoing substance formed *acetyl* derivative as hexagonal plates from dilute methyl alcohol, m. p. 150.52°. ($C_{15}H_{17}O_3NCl_3Br$ requires Halogen, 41.8. Found: Halogen, 42.1 per cent).

2-Methyl-4-(α -hydroxy- β -trichloroethyl)-6-chloro-N-methylaniline.—The powdered hydrochloride of *p*-(α -hydroxy- β -trichloroethyl)-*o*-methyltoluidine (16 g.) was suspended in dry benzene (50 c. c.) and dry chlorine passed through the mixture under stirring for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, yield 12 g. The base was obtained by treatment with ammonia and crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol, m. p. 132.33°. (Found: Cl, 47.1. $C_{10}H_{11}ONCl_4$ requires Cl, 46.9 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol, m. p. 112°. (Found: Cl, 38.5. $C_{14}H_{15}O_3NCl_4$ requires Cl, 38.3 per cent).

2-Methyl-4-(α -hydroxy- β -trichloroethyl)-6-chloro-N-ethylaniline.—The powdered hydrochloride of *p*-(α -hydroxy- β -trichloroethyl)-*o*-ethyltoluidine (20 g.) was treated with chlorine. The hydrochloride thus obtained was basified with ammonia and crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol as prismatic needles, m. p. 116.17°, yield 14 g. (Found: Cl, 44.6. $C_{11}H_{13}ONCl_4$ requires Cl, 44.8 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol, m. p. 155.56°. (Found: Cl, 35.2. $C_{15}H_{17}O_3NCl_4$ requires Cl, 35.4 per cent).

2-Methyl-4-(α -hydroxy- β -trichloroethyl-6-bromophenyl)-N-methyl-nitroamine.—*2-Methyl-4-(α -hydroxy- β -trichloroethyl)-6-bromo-N-methylaniline* (5 g.) was treated with strong nitric acid (15 c. c.). The filtered precipitate was kept in *vacuo* over alkali for 48 hours and crystallised from dilute ethyl alcohol as prismatic needles, m. p. 230° (decomp.), yield 5 g. ($C_{10}H_{10}O_3N_2Cl_3Br$ requires Halogen, 47.5. Found: Halogen, 47.2 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol, m. p. 107°. ($C_{12}H_{12}O_4N_2Cl_3Br$ requires Halogen, 42.8. Found: Halogen, 42.6 per cent).

2-Methyl-4-(α -hydroxy- β -trichloroethyl)-6-bromophenyl-N-ethyl-nitroamine.—2-Methyl-4-(α -hydroxy- β -trichloroethyl)-6-bromo-*N*-ethylaniline (5 g.) when treated with strong nitric acid furnished after crystallisation from dilute ethyl alcohol thin needles, m.p. 198° (decomp.), yield 4 g. ($C_{11}H_{12}O_3N_2Cl_3Br$ requires Halogen, 45.9. Found: Halogen 45.5 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol, m.p. 127°. ($C_{13}H_{14}O_4N_2Cl_3Br$ requires Halogen, 41.6. Found: Halogen, 41.7 per cent.).

2-Methyl-4-(α -hydroxy- β -trichloroethyl)-6-chlorophenyl-N-methyl-nitroamine.—2-Methyl-4-(α -hydroxy- β -trichloroethyl)-6-chloro-*N*-methylaniline (5 g.) was treated with warm strong nitric acid (6 c.c.). The crystalline nitroamine which separated on cooling, crystallised from a mixture of acetone and dilute ethyl alcohol as clusters of small needles which change colour at 210° and decompose at 230°, yield 4.5 g. (Found: Cl, 40.5. $C_{10}H_{10}O_3N_2Cl_4$ requires Cl, 40.8 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from dilute ethyl alcohol as clusters of needles, m.p. 113°. (Found: Cl, 36.1. $C_{12}H_{12}O_4N_2Cl_4$ requires Cl, 36.4 per cent.).

2-Methyl-4-(α -hydroxy- β -trichloroethyl)-6-chloro-phenyl-N-ethyl-nitroamine.—2-Methyl-4-(α -hydroxy- β -trichloroethyl)-6-chloro-*N*-ethylaniline was treated with strong nitric acid and the mixture heated until nitrous fumes began to evolve when the solid nitroamine separated. It crystallised from a mixture of acetone, methyl alcohol and water in thin needles, m.p. 181°. (Found: Cl, 39.0. $C_{11}H_{12}O_3N_2Cl_4$ requires Cl, 39.2 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol in clusters of colourless needles, m.p. 132°. (Found: Cl, 35.0. $C_{13}H_{14}O_4N_2Cl_4$ requires Cl, 35.1 per cent.).

2-Methyl-4-(α -chloro- β -trichloroethyl)-6-nitrophenyl-N-methylnitroamine.—2-Methyl-4-(α -hydroxy- β -trichloroethyl)-6-nitrophenyl-*N*-methylamine (3 g.) was treated with thionyl chloride (15 c.c.) and the mixture refluxed on a water-bath at 50° for 3 hours. After removal of thionyl chloride, the thick liquid solidified in *vacuo* over alkali. It crystallised from absolute alcohol, m.p. 199°. (Found: Cl, 29.6. $C_{10}H_9O_4N_3Cl_4$ requires Cl, 29.9 per cent.).